

Table 1. Characters and yields of Mashuri and some local Cuu Long Delta rice varieties, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Variety	Character	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Lodging (0-9)	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
							1980	1981	1982
Mashuri		150	132	264	230	3	3.7 a	4.0 a	5.4 a
Trang Lun	Acid sulfate tolerance	190	148	247	86	4	3.1 b	3.8 a	5.5 a
Trang Chum	Deepwater	180	137	204	124	5	3.1 b	3.7 a	–
Tieu Doi	Salinity tolerance	176	116	192	152	7	–	–	5.0 a
Nang Huong	Good quality	173	157	145	107	9	–	–	2.1 b

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% level.

Table 2. Reaction^a of Mashuri to rice pests in the Cuu Long Delta, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Variety	BPH		B1		BLB		ShB	
	Infestation (%)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction
Mashuri	88	HS	2-6	R-MS	4	MS	9	HS
Trang Lun	85	HS	4-5	MS	3	MR	7	S
Trang Chum	85	HS	4-6	MS	3	MR	7	S
Resistant C ^b	26	MR	1	R	1	R	7	S
Susceptible C ^b	100	HS	4-9	MS-HS	8	S	9	HS

^aArtificial infestation, using IRRI test and scoring procedures: R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^bResistant check for BPH = IR36, B1 = Te Tep. BLB = Cempo Selak. ShB = IET4699. Susceptible check for BPH = TN1. B1 = NN 7A, BLB = 1R8, ShB = IR36.

(B1) and bacterial leaf blight (BLB) (Table 2). In the monsoon season, when late-maturing varieties are grown, we expect Mashuri will not have severe pest problems.

Because of Mashuri's favorable performance, we are carrying out a large-scale seed multiplication program in cooperation with provincial agricultural departments. □

Measurement of seedling height in rice varieties and breeding lines

K. T. Nwe, research scholar, and D. J. Mackill, associate plant breeder, IRRI

Seedling or vegetative vigor is an important trait for direct-seeded and transplanted rainfed lowland conditions and is usually measured visually in the field some time after transplanting. Seedling height is an important component of seedling vigor. We studied the relationship between seedling height measured in plants grown in a seedbox and plant height at 20 d after transplanting (DT), mature plant height, and days to 50% heading of plants grown in a concrete bed in the field.

Pregenninated seeds of 20 genotypes (including traditional and semidwarf varieties and breeding lines) were sown in single rows in seedboxes in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Seedling height of individual seedlings was measured 7, 14, 21, and 28 d after seeding (DAS). Twenty-one-day-old seedlings were transplanted in single rows in the concrete bed.

The ranking of varieties for seedling height differed little for each measure-

Seedling height at 21 DAS, plant height at 21 DT, mature plant height, and days to 50% heading for 20 rice varieties and breeding lines, IRRI.

Variety	Seedling ht (cm) 21 DAS ^a	Plant ht (cm) 21 DT	Mature plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% heading
Aungzeya	41.7 a	89.7	176.0	72
Black Gora	40.8 a	92.8	157.0	73
Shwedinga	39.3 ab	79.0	158.8	87
Nam Sagui 19	37.6 bc	90.2	146.0	63
Emata	35.9 cd	93.8	153.6	99
D25-4	33.2 de	73.5	121.0	89
Ngwetoe	33.1 de	87.5	136.0	65
5207	32.7 e	77.2	134.2	88
IR14632-22-3	31.3 ef	64.0	117.4	88
IR19248-76-2-1-3	30.7 efg	72.5	121.4	87
IR32	30.1 fg	60.2	110.6	97
IR52	29.3 fgh	66.8	108.4	78
IR34	28.3 ghi	69.3	113.8	84
IR14753-49-3	27.8 ghi	61.5	119.2	80
IR520-2-1-6	27.3 hij	62.7	108.2	85
BR319-1	26.5 hijk	69.3	144.6	82
IR13564-95-1	26.2 ijk	62.0	70.4	55
ITA 141	25.0 jk	72.3	130.4	82
IR19242-58-2-3-2	24.2 k	63.7	127.8	88
IR50	23.9 k	61.0	94.2	72

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

ment date. The CVs for 7, 14, 21, and 28 DAS were 14.7, 6.8, 5.5, and 7.8%. The 21-d measurement gave the most reliable results.

Data for seedling height at 21 DAS, plant height at 21 DT, mature plant height, and days to 50% heading are in the table. Seedling height at 21 DAS was highly correlated with both plant height

at 21 DT ($r = 0.83$) and mature plant height ($r = 0.75$). The correlation with days to 50% heading was not significant ($r = -0.05$). The seedling box measurement appears to be an accurate estimate of plant height at 21 DT in the field.

For rainfed lowland conditions it would be useful to have plants of intermediate stature with tall seedlings. As

can be seen from the high positive correlation between seedling height and mature plant height, shortening of tall

traditional varieties by breeding can be expected to reduce seedling height. The Burmese variety D25-4 had good seed-

ling height while maintaining a relatively lower mature plant height. □

Flowering induction in photoperiod-sensitive rices which are potential donors of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) resistance

J. P. Singh, H. Singh, S. C. Mani, and J. S. Nanda, Plant Breeding Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, U. P., India

Many traditional tall and photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties have genes for resistance to various stresses and can be used as donors. But their usefulness in breeding programs at higher latitudes is limited because they either do not flower or flower late and die of cold. With appropriate photoperiod treatments, such varieties could be induced to flower early and could be used in hybridization programs.

Balamawee, Ptb 19, ARC6624, ARC6579, ARC10464, ARC11321, and ARC11324 are potential donors of genes for resistance to WBPH (*Sogatella furcifera*), but they are photoperiod sensitive and do not flower at Pantnagar

Photoperiod response of different rice varieties at Pantnagar, India.

Variety	Days to flowering					
	70-d-old seedlings ^a		56-d-old seedlings ^b		Control ^c	
	10 h photoperiod	9 h photoperiod	10 h photoperiod	9h photoperiod	DS 28 May 82	DS 11 Jun 82
Balamawee	96	97	89	89	No flowering	No flowering
Ptb19	105	106	88	89	No flowering	No flowering
ARC6624	103	101	88	89	154	141
ARC6579	102	101	88	88	154	141
ARC10464	101	102	88	88	141	128
ARC11321	102	104	89	88	153	139
ARC11324	105	105	91	90	152	139

^a Sown 28 May 1982. ^b Sown 11 Jun 1982. ^c DS = direct seeded.

(29°N lat. and 79.3°E long.).

We tested artificial methods of flower induction. Varieties were planted 28 May and 11 Jun 1982. To induce flowering at 70 d for the first date and 56 d for the second, seedlings were placed in dark chambers for 10 and 9 h photoperiod treatment. One set of seedlings from each date of sowing also was transplanted in the field as a control.

When planted on 28 May, all varieties with 10 h photoperiod flowered in 96 to 105 d and those with 9 h photoperiod in 97 to 106 d (see table). When planted

11 Jun, the same varieties flowered in 88 to 91 d with 10 h photoperiod and 88 to 90 d with 9 photoperiod. In the field, flowering duration varied from 141 to 154 d in the May sowing and from 128 to 141 d in the June sowing. Balamawee and Ptb 19 did not flower in the field.

Flowering duration did not differ for 10 and 9 h photoperiod. Photoperiod cycles varied from 26 to 36 in the 28 May sowing and from 33 to 35 in the 11 Jun sowing. Fifty-six-d-old seedlings flowered earlier than 70-d-old ones. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Free-choice and no-choice seedling bulk tests for evaluating resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

R. C. Saxena, associate entomologist, IRRI, and principal research scientist, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Nairobi, Kenya; and Z. R. Khan, postdoctoral fellow in Entomology, IRRI

A free-choice seedling bulk test is routinely used for mass screening of rice germplasm to identify donors of resistance to rice leafhoppers and planthoppers. It is relatively simple, inexpensive, and fairly reliable when dealing

Table 1. Settling behavior^a of WBPH nymphs on seedlings of susceptible and resistant rice varieties in a free-choice screening test, IRRI, 1983.

Variety	Nymphs (%) that settled on seedlings at indicated h after infestation ^b			
	1	8	24	48
ADR52	4.2 a	6.2 cde	6.5 bc	6.0 c
ARC10239	4.5 a	6.3 cd	5.5 d	6.0 c
Colombo	4.5 a	5.8 de	6.4 cd	6.6 c
Muskhan 41	4.4 a	6.9 bc	7.1 bc	6.5 c
N22	4.4 a	7.1 bc	7.3 bc	6.5 c
N32	4.3 a	6.5 bcd	6.7 bc	5.9 c
IR2035-117-3	4.2 a	5.3 e	5.6 d	6.2 c
Podiwi A8	4.2 a	7.3 b	7.5 b	7.6 b
WC1240	4.1 a	6.6 bcd	6.3 cd	6.4 c
TN1 (susceptible check)	4.5 a	14.1 a	19.6 a	20.7 a

^a Percentage calculated on total number of insects released in a seedbox and remaining insects on the soil below the seedlings. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level; av of 5 replications, 750 nymphs/seedbox.